

Towards cooked meat less loaded in heterocyclic aromatic amines but sensorially acceptable!

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Abstract

Formulation by adding antioxidants is a promising lever for reducing the formation of heterocyclic aromatic amines (HAAs), incriminated in the development of colorectal cancers. A unique and original method based on medicinal chemistry approaches was thus developed and permitted to select antioxidants best suited to inhibit HAA formation in meat: caper, oregano, red wine and green tea. The aim of the present work is to evaluate the sensory acceptability of the formulations tested for their HAA content and determine the odour-active compounds incriminated in the potential differences, in order to select formulations representing the best compromise between mitigation solution for process-induced toxicants and sensory acceptability. Firstly, a hedonic study was done to determine which formulations among the 4 tested were the most appreciated by consumers. Then non-verbal analyses were done to assess to what extent these hedonic differences were attributable to sensory differences. To characterize these differences, a fast sensory profiling was done followed by gas-chromatography-olfactometry (GC-8O) to identify the odour-active compounds responsible for these differences. This paper permitted to evidence the best balance between health benefit and sensory inconvenience and to assess the best option of formulation.

Keywords: hedonic rating, non-verbal analysis, fast sensory profiling, gas-chromatography-olfactometry

Introduction

In 2015, the consumption of red meat has been classified as probably carcinogenic (group 2A) for Human by the International Agency for Research on Cancer [1] and heterocyclic aromatic amines (HAAs) have been identified among the process-induced toxicants responsible. Mitigation strategies to reduce HAA impact on human health were proposed and one of the most promising was the addition of natural antioxidants to limit HAA formation [2]. But to date there is no method for making a reasoned choice of antioxidants. Therefore, in the first part of this work [3] a unique and original method based on medicinal chemistry approaches was developed to select antioxidants best suited to inhibit HAA formation in meat. This method allowed a rationalization of the choice of antioxidants to optimize meat chemical safety but it would only be admissible if these antioxidants are sensorially validated as the addition of antioxidants should in no way modify the sensory acceptance of the product or be subject to its rejection by consumers. Previous works studying the sensorial effect of the addition of antioxidants in meat often used descriptive analysis [4, 5] but such method is long and expensive as it requires a deeply trained panel. To circumvent these issues the present work develops an original strategy using hedonic studies, non-verbal and quantitative descriptive analyses and gas-chromatography-olfactometry (GC-8O) in order to determine what drives consumer's acceptance and to identify the sensory determinants that are at the origin of the latter. This strategy is implemented to compare the sensory effects of the addition of the 4 natural ingredients rich in phenolic antioxidants evidenced by the first part of this work [3]: caper, oregano, red wine and green tea.

Experimental

Hedonic scoring

Fifty-nine meat consumers were recruited to participate in two sessions over a period of two weeks. For each session the samples formulations were composed of two different natural products rich in antioxidants at two concentrations and a standard. The samples were coded with a 3-digit number and given in a monadic way to be rated on a 9-point hedonic scale (1, dislike extremely; 5, neither like nor dislike; 9, extremely pleasant).

Direct dissimilarity assessment

The non-verbal procedures used in this research work were directly inspired by Bonaïti et al. [6]. Fifteen selected panellists were instructed to estimate the overall dissimilarity between samples by positioning them in a square paper map of 60 x 60cm. This part was divided into two sessions in the same week. The first session only assessed overall dissimilarity while the second assessed olfactive and gustative dissimilarity. Samples were presented in the centre of the paper and panellists were allowed to smell and/or taste the samples as many times as

they wanted without respecting any specific order. In this non-verbal analysis, panellists were asked to place the formulations on a white sheet of paper based on their dissimilarities in terms of flavour and odour. Coordinates were calculated for each sample and each assessor. The largest between-sample distance was used to normalize distances that were obtained from each panellist. Normalized distances were then compiled to obtain an average distance matrix. The results were analysed through multidimensional scaling (MDS).

Fast sensory profiling

The panellists from the previous step were trained during an orientation session and came back two days later to evaluate the samples based on the training session instructions. The aim of the first session was to develop descriptive terms that could describe each sample and agree on the definition of each term. The session was monitored in order to agree on a consensual vocabulary. The final list was composed of 16 terms describing taste (4), texture (2) and aroma (10). In the second session, semi-trained panellists received the concentrations chosen in the hedonic step, including two standards (unmarinated and water marinated) and were instructed to rate the intensity of each term using a 10 cm unstructured linear scale from 'no perception' to 'strong perception'. For this session, the samples were presented in a monadic way to balance report and position effects.

Gas Chromatography/Mass spectrometry – olfactometry

Beef patties (four formulations rich in antioxidants, one standard and one water-marinated standard) were prepared and stored at -80°C. The day before the analyses, the samples were thawed at -4°C overnight. The next morning, they were cooked under same conditions than previous samples [3]. Ten grams of cooked sample were taken, 5 g from the centre of the steak and 5 g from the edge with some juice to be representative of the whole sample. Condensed volatile compounds were analysed by GC-O (model 6890; Hewlett-Packard, Avondale, PA). The volatile compounds were extracted by dynamic headspace (Tekmar, Cincinnati, OH, USA) coupled to gas chromatography (GC 4890D, Agilent Technologies) according to Giri et al. [7]. The sample was purged with helium (purity 99.995%) at 30°C for 1h with a flow rate of 40 mL.min⁻¹ using a Tenax trap. After injection, volatiles were separated and smelled according to Berdagué et al. [8]. The unique GC-8O system accumulates the performance of 8 judges simultaneously on the same sample to detect what are the most significant odour zones in the chromatogram. The selected sniffers were non-smokers with no known health disorders and with tested sensitivity and ability to detect and consistently describe a wide range of odours. They were advised to stay away from coffee or food 3 hours prior to the manipulation. The sniffers were asked to signal each odorous passage and provide one descriptor and its corresponding intensity on a five-level scale (1, very weak; 3, moderate; 5, very strong) [8]. This manipulation took place over 6 sessions of 35 min with the first one using water-marinated sample to familiarise the panellists and to give them a baseline. Olfactometric data were acquired and processed with the AcquiSniff® software [9]. Coupled with mass spectrometry, the GC-8O enables to identify the odour-active compounds and to assess their contribution to the overall odour/aroma of the product.

Data analysis

Data were analysed using Statistica software 10.0 (Statsoft, Maisons-Alfort, France) and AcquiSniff® software (INRA, Clermont-Ferrand, France). Hedonic mean scores were compared using Duncan's test. Direct dissimilarity assessment data were analysed by MDS mapping as proposed by Bonaïti et al. [6].

Results and discussion

Acceptability of the different formulations: Hedonic rating

This first part of the study aimed at determining the most preferred formulations among the panellists and permitted to guide the following sensory experiments. The four formulations (caper, oregano, green tea and wine) at two different concentrations were tested by the panellists along with a standard. The results displayed in figure 1 showed a great disparity of the hedonic scores between the formulations. The standard was the most preferred with respect to food neophobia often reported for novel foods [10]. Interestingly, two formulations, caper 0.5% and oregano 0.25 %, were non-significantly different from the standards. This can be due to the relative congruence of capers and oregano with ground beef patties. From Figure 1, wine and tea did confer a change that was noticeable by consumers as they rated those formulations as the least preferred. Our findings are in accordance with the results of Melo et al. [4] showing that longer marinating time in wine (4 to 6h) would generate unpleasant wine aroma, strong red colour and poor overall quality, contrary to 2h marinating time which resulted in no to little notable differences in sensorial perceptions [4, 5]. Moreover, the low hedonic scores of wine and tea formulations can again be related to the food neophobia phenomenon as those products are not usually used for ground beef preparations in our occidental countries.

Figure 1: Mean values obtained for the 8 formulations by hedonic rating using a 9-point hedonic scale.

Given the results of hedonic scoring, the formulations chosen for the next part of the work were the less concentrated in order to be as close as possible of household practices.

Sensory dimensions responsible for the differences of acceptability

- Non-verbal dissimilarity rating

In order to explain the hedonic scoring of our formulations, non-verbal analysis was used to make the link between the odorous compounds and the acceptance. The results of MDS are displayed in figure 2.

Figure 2: Positioning of the 4 formulations and 2 standards according to their flavour or odour: a) 2-D multidimensional scaling of the average distance matrix based on 2D flavour dissimilarity assessment; b) 2-D multidimensional scaling of the average distance matrix based on 2D odour dissimilarity assessment.

A MDS mapping of flavour dissimilarities was undertaken (Figure 2a) to determine if flavour plays an important role in the differentiation of the formulations. A similar non-verbal analysis focused on the smell was also produced (Figure 2b) to know if the smell plays a key role in the differentiation on the flavour, as understanding the contribution of the odour on the discrimination is essential. The MDS map of the flavour

dissimilarity profile (Figure 2a) clearly showed that wine and oregano formulations were different between themselves (dimension 1) and to the others (dimension 2). Caper formulation, marinated standard and standard were closely related in the second dimension and tea preparation, although close to this second group, was slightly different in the second dimension. Similar results were found for odour dissimilarity profile (Figure 2b). Non-verbal results highlighted the dissimilarity between oregano and standard formulations but as oregano is congruent with meat preparation, these sensorial differences didn't result in consumer rejection. On the contrary, as wine and to a lesser extent tea are not congruent with meat preparation, the sensory differences highlighted in the non-verbal results could explain their low acceptability (as shown by the hedonic rating). It seems that the other two chemical senses contributing to flavour (gustatory and trigeminal) contribute little to the differences in flavour profiles evidenced by non-verbal analysis. As a result, this research will focus on the olfactive dimension to find the molecular determinants responsible for the difference of acceptability.

- Fast sensory profiling

Table 1: Comparison of the attribute intensities measured by fast sensory profiling for the 2 standards and 4 formulations according to the 2-way ANOVA. The table presents only the attributes for which the p-value of the product effect is <0.01 or <0.005 and the relative judge effect is not significant.

	<i>Standard</i>	<i>Marinated Standard</i>	<i>Green Tea formulation</i>	<i>Caper formulation</i>	<i>Oregano formulation</i>	<i>Wine formulation</i>
<i>Grilled</i>	$4.0 \pm 2.8^{a,b}$	$4.9 \pm 2.4^{a,b}$	$2.9 \pm 2.1^{b,c}$	5.7 ± 3.1^a	$4.8 \pm 2.2^{a,b}$	1.8 ± 2.1^c
<i>Aromatic Plants</i>	0.3 ± 0.6^b	0.2 ± 0.3^b	0.3 ± 0.8^b	0.5 ± 1.0^b	7.8 ± 2.2^a	0.7 ± 1.8^b
<i>Winy</i>	0.1 ± 0.2^c	1.2 ± 2.5^c	2.8 ± 3.4^b	0.3 ± 0.6^c	0.3 ± 0.6^c	8.2 ± 2.0^a
<i>Juiciness</i>	5.3 ± 2.8^a	2.6 ± 2.0^b	2.4 ± 1.8^b	$3.9 \pm 2.5^{a,b}$	$3.9 \pm 2.7^{a,b}$	4.9 ± 2.7^a

The results from the sensory profiling (Table 1) permitted to evaluate the nature of the differences highlighted by non-verbal analyses. Based on this fast sensory profiling, the winy attribute, not congruent for proteinaceous foods, explained the result of the non-verbal analysis and permitted to discriminate wine and to a lesser extent green tea formulation from the others. In contrast, the aromatic plant note, which is congruent with meat products, permitted to differentiate oregano formulation from the others.

Odour-active drivers of the acceptability differences between the studied formulations

- Qualitative comparison of the aromagrams of the different formulations

When comparing the different aromagrams (Figure 3), the wine and oregano formulations showed the highest variation with the standard which explained the differences observed in MDS analyses. The “green/aromatic plant” note at 950s present in the aromagram of the standard was absent in both wine and oregano formulations. This peak corresponds to hexanal which is an oxidation product. Its disappearance in both formulations can be related to the antioxidant activities of wine and oregano. The wine formulation was distinguished by a strong contribution of fruity/floral notes which could be related to esters, benzaldehyde or linalool previously reported in Pinot Noir [11]. These differences observed in the aromagrams of wine formulation and standard were consistent with the fast sensory profiling results showing more important fruity and wine attributes in wine formulation. The oregano aromagram was differentiated by high intensity poles (>3.5) “butter/lactic/cheese” and “vegetable”.

Figure 3. Mean aromagrams of (A) Standard (B) Oregano (C) Wine calculated from 8 individual sniffing sessions. The breakdown of the signal into twelve odour classes shows the odorant zones belonging to a given olfactory class.

- Identification of discriminant volatile compounds for each formulation

Table 2 presents the main distinctive peaks of the different formulations obtained by coupling GC-O and GC/MS data. The matching of the resulting candidate compounds and the odour descriptors generated by the trained panellists was assessed thanks to a library of aroma descriptors and retention time found at thegoodsentcompany.com and the nature of the peaks was proposed (Table 2).

Table 2. Nature of the significant peaks of the different formulations obtained by coupling GC-O and GC/MS data with LRI: Linear Retention Indices; S: standard formulation; W: wine formulation; O: oregano formulation; C: caper formulation; T: green tea formulation.

Peak	LRI	Chemical Name	Odour Descriptor	Formulations				
				S	W	O	C	T
3	829	Ethyl isobutyrate	Fruity, strawberry candy, citrus		X			
6	1002	Ethyl-2-hydroxypropanoate	Caramel, bread crust, grilled beef				X	
7	1099	Ethyl-2-methylbutanoate	Strawberry, sour candies		X			
9	1308	2,3-dimethyl-pyrazine	Cold cuts, peanut, ham, mushroom			X		X
11	1428	4-methyl-cyclohexanone	Mint, sulfur, chemical, fruity		X			
		heptanol						
		benzaldehyde						

14	1626	1,8-cineole	Grass, caramel, mint					
16	1755	Ethyl heptanoate	Sausage, fermented grass, butyric acid, floral, rind, mustiness			X		X
		3-ethyl-2,5-dimethyl pyrazine						
		2-nonanone						
17	1819	Unknown	Grilled meat, sausage, grilled peanut, butter			X		X
18	1824	Dimethyltrisulfide isomer	Sausage, ham butter sandwich, smoked lard, roasted, broth, pizza, warm chicken, mustiness	X	X		X	
		2-Phenylethanol						
19	1904	Methyl-2-methyl-3-furyl-disulfide	Green leaf, burnt paper, fermented grass, vegetable, floral			X		X
20	2001	Ethyl octanoate	Sausage, ham, potato, coffee, broth					

Peaks 3 and 7, both described with fruity descriptors and found in wine formulation, seemed distinctive from the other formulations. Ethyl isobutyrate (peak 3) and ethyl-2-methylbutanoate (peak 7) confirmed the strong contribution of fruity/floral notes previously observed in figure 3. Their presence in wine formulation was coherent with previous studies as they resulted from the fermentation process [11]. Peak 18 distinguished wine from oregano and green tea formulations. Peaks 9, 16, 17 and 19 found in oregano and green tea seemed distinctive from standard formulation. The presence of 2,3-dimethylpyrazine (peak 9) explained the overexpression of the vegetable note at 1280s in oregano and green tea aromagrams compared to standard and is consistent with the work of Zhu et al. [12] who detected several pyrazines in green tea samples. Peak 6 found in caper formulation seemed distinctive from the other formulations. The presence of ethyl-2-hydroxypropanoate (peak 6) was therefore a marker for this formulation as evidenced by the overexpression of the “butter/lactic/cheese” note at 1000-1030 s in caper aromagram compared to the standard.

Conclusion

Based on this work, we could now determine that oregano would be the best choice as at medium concentration it displays a strong congruence with ground beef patties and presents an acceptability comparable to that of the target product, as to know cooked meat. The approach proposed here made it possible to select among 4 formulations the one which was the most realistic from the point of view of sensory acceptability. These data will allow the oregano model, or in any case its active principle, to be used to subsequently elucidate the mechanism of inhibition of the formation of HAAs and the impact of this formulation on colorectal carcinogenesis in connection with exposure to HAAs.

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